

1 **Reassessment of immunologically-restricted gene expression in solid tumors in humans.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We provide here a brief summary of a collection of findings that together demonstrate a poorly understood
7 and underappreciated concept that genes whose expression is generally described to be restricted to cells
8 of the hematopoietic compartment or to cells of the immune system can be and are expressed in normal,
9 non-hematopoietically derived tissues of the body I, and in solid tumors. We previously demonstrated that
10 both for the exhaustion-associated genes BTLA, ICOS and TIGIT, as well as for the
11 lymphocyte-associated genes IGK and IGKV, changes in gene expression measured and described were
12 not a result of contamination or infiltration of bulk tumor tissue samples with tumor-infiltrating or
13 -associated lymphocytes, rather tumor cell-intrinsic gene expression. Immunologically or
14 hematopoietically-restricted genes with expression in non-hematopoietic tissues and in cancer of solid
15 tissues include those expressed in the platelet, including clotting factors FXII. Gene expression of products
16 from the interferon pathway, of the IFI, IFIT and IFITM families, and genes expressed by antigen
17 presenting cells encoded by the major histocompatibility complex class I and II regions are also important
18 gene expression events described and understood to be restricted to the hematopoietic compartment but
19 which we have found are specific expression features of non-hematopoietic cells and tissues in cancer
20 and normal health. These are important biological concepts that have implications in development and in
21 a failed ability to control transformation by the immune system that results in metastasis and death from
22 cancer.

23 **References**

24 Mamoor, S., 2020. The immunoglobulin light chain kappa locus is differentially expressed in the primary
25 tumors of patients with breast cancer and this is an intrinsic transcriptional feature of the primary tumor.

26 Mamoor, S., 2023. Tumor cell-intrinsic expression of BTLA, ICOS and TIGIT in human breast cancer.

27 Beyaz S, Chung C, Mou H, Bauer-Rowe KE, Xifaras ME, Ergin I, Dohnalova L, Biton M, Shekhar K,
28 Eskiocak O, Papciak K, Ozler K, Almeqdadı M, Yueh B, Fein M, Annamalai D, Valle-Encinas E, Erdemir A,
Dogum K, Shah V, Alici-Garipcan A, Meyer HV, Özata DM, Elinav E, Kucukural A, Kumar P, McAleer JP,
Fox JG, Thaiss CA, Regev A, Roper J, Orkin SH, Yilmaz ÖH. Dietary suppression of MHC class II
expression in intestinal epithelial cells enhances intestinal tumorigenesis. Cell Stem Cell. 2021 Nov
4;28(11):1922-1935.e5. doi: 10.1016/j.stem.2021.08.007. Epub 2021 Sep 15. PMID: 34529935; PMCID:
PMC8650761.